

Scheduling wagons to unload in bulk cargo ports with uncertain processing times

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Abstract

Optimising operations in bulk cargo ports is of great relevance due to their major participation in international trade. In inbound operations, which are critical to meet due dates, the product typically arrives by train and must be transferred to the stockyard. This process requires several machines and is subject to frequent disruptions leading to uncertain processing times. This work focuses on the scheduling problem of unloading the wagons to the stockyard, approaching both the deterministic and the stochastic versions. For the deterministic problem, we compare three solution approaches: a Mixed Integer Programming model, a Constraint Programming model and a Greedy Randomised algorithm. The selection rule of the latter is evolved by Genetic Programming. The stochastic version is approached by dispatching rules, also evolved via Genetic Programming. The proposed approaches are validated using real data from a leading company in the mining sector. Results show that the new heuristic presents similar results to the company's algorithm in a considerably shorter computational time. Moreover, we perform extensive computational experiments to validate the methods on a wide spectrum of randomly generated instances. Finally, as managing uncertainty is fundamental for the effectiveness of these operations, distinct strategies are compared, ranging from purely predictive to completely reactive scheduling. We conclude that re-scheduling with high frequency is the best approach to avoid performance deterioration under schedule disruptions, and using the evolved dispatching rules incur fewer deviations from the original schedule.

Keywords: Dynamic Scheduling, Bulk Cargo Ports, Dispatching Rules, Genetic Programming

1. Introduction

One-third of the global maritime trade operates dry bulk cargo like iron ore, coal and grains (e.g., wheat and soybean). In particular, iron ore shipments amounted to 1.4 billion tons in 2019, corresponding to 8% of the total maritime volume (UNCTAD, 2020). Ports are critical for iron ore producers as demand is mainly fulfilled overseas to steel companies. Given their inherent complexity involving several assets (e.g., railways) and processes (e.g., product blending), ports are commonly the bottleneck of iron ore supply chains (Comtois and Slack, 2016).

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Dry bulk ports usually serve as export or import terminals exclusively. Export terminals have three subsystems: the product income, the stockyard and the berths. All of them manage complex operations and are subject to uncertainty. Most research efforts have concentrated on the berths and neglected the inbound operations (Neagoe et al., 2018). Hence, the problem of assigning vessels to berths is well-studied and known as the Berth Allocation Problem (BAP). Some works on the specific case of bulk cargo are found, including particular features as the stock levels and blending (Barros et al., 2011; Umang et al., 2013; Bilgen and Ozkarahan, 2007). The BAP has also been integrated with other operations, especially in real-world problems. For instance, Menezes et al. (2017) and Robenek et al. (2014) approach case studies from Brazil and middle-east, respectively. In both cases, they solve the integrated planning of the berths, stockyard allocation and product income. Rocha de Paula et al. (2019) and Burdett et al. (2020) study and solve the operations of the three subsystems in terminals from Australia. However, in these works, the inbound resources are considered only for capacity checking – in hourly time buckets. The scheduling of machines and tools for wagons unloading has not been addressed so far, a major gap which we aim to address.

In large export terminals, the product is dumped from trains to stockpiles, which requires a route of machines (e.g., a car dumper, conveyor belts and stackers). The schedule includes several routes that share the same machines and must work in parallel. It is challenging to assign routes to wagons and sequence them without conflicts. Moreover, one must satisfy trains' arrivals and railway maneuvers. Research is needed to find effective scheduling methods to optimise the throughput of these inbound operations. Besides synchronising several machines and avoiding conflicts in the routes, managers must also deal with unexpected disruptions. The process is frequently interrupted by machine breakdowns, arrivals of urgent operations or interdiction of some location in the stockyard. Therefore, in addition to generating effective schedules, providing adequate responses to interruptions is also relevant. As the process involves maneuvers, managers must also prevent the overhead caused by several modifications to the base schedule. This study aims at developing high-quality initial solutions (deterministic case) and approaches for responding to unexpected disruptions and minimising deviations from the original schedule (stochastic case).

Our paper provides multiple contributions to the study of bulk cargo operations. First, we introduce and formalise a new problem found in export terminals - the Wagon Unloading Problem. Solution methods are proposed for both the deterministic and the stochastic versions of the problem. The effectiveness of these methods is demonstrated in extensive computational experiments. We use real data from two of the world largest iron ore ports, solving huge scheduling problems of hundreds of machines. Moreover, we analyse the performance of dispatching rules and predictive-reactive strategies using a stochastic simulation model. This analysis extends previous works by tackling the trade-off between maximising performance and minimising deviations from a baseline schedule (Jain and Foley, 2016).

The Wagon Unloading Problem is modelled as a variant of the Multimode Multiprocessor Task Scheduling Problem (MMTSP), where each task has distinct execution modes (Drozdowski, 2009). In the application tackled here, tasks are unloading operations, and each possible route is an execution mode. Additional constraints are incorporated to address the specificities of the problem, such as trains' arrivals and railway maneuvers. We present a Mixed Integer

Programming formulation and a Constraint Programming model for the deterministic version. Moreover, we design a greedy-randomised heuristic using Genetic Programming (GP), an evolutionary hyper-heuristic that has been successfully applied to production scheduling (Nguyen et al., 2017). GP is employed on the generation of priority rules that are used to select operations in the constructive heuristic. We hypothesise that even well-performing deterministic methods deteriorate solution quality in the stochastic context. Thus, we evaluate three approaches: following the baseline schedule, re-scheduling, and using dispatching rules (designed by GP). All these methods are tested in instances from real ports, and we also use a set of randomly generated instances to represent an extensive range of scenarios and different uncertainty levels.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 briefly describes the literature on the MMTSP and similar problems. As we also deal with the stochastic version of the problem, we present the main approaches adopted to cope with uncertainty in scheduling. In Section 3, the Wagon Unloading Problem is described in detail. The exact models are presented in Section 4.1. First, we present the Mixed Integer Programming formulation and then the Constraint Programming model. Section 5 concerns the Genetic Programming algorithm. We describe the greedy-randomised heuristic and how we use the priority and dispatching rules. We also detail the specific GP developed for this work. Section 6 describes the experiments design, the instance sets and the algorithm parameters. The computational results are presented in Section 7, where we describe the evolved rules and compare the performance of the proposed approaches. We also present the performance of dispatching rules and other approaches under uncertainty. Conclusions and future work are given in Section 8.

2. Background

Multiprocessor Task Scheduling Problems (MTSP) is a class of scheduling problems in which some tasks are executed simultaneously by more than one resource. Applications are found in parallel computing systems, where jobs are distributed among several processors (Switalski and Seredynski, 2015), in some variants of the BAP when a ship requires more than one quay crane (Türkoğullar et al., 2014), and in workforce allocation when operation times depend on the number of workers assigned (Battaia et al., 2015). Drozdowski (2009) presents an extensive review and classification of the distinct MTSP variants.

The Multimode Multiprocessor Task Scheduling Problem (MMTSP) is a variant of MTSP in which tasks have multiple execution modes. Each mode comprises a subset of machines and a specific processing time. Although several applications may be found in the industry, the problem received little attention from scheduling literature. Błażewicz et al. (1992) prove that the problem is NP-hard by showing that the particular case with three machines is strongly NP-hard. Meta-heuristics based on intensification and diversification were developed in the work of Caramia and Giordani (2009) and Caramia and Giordani (2010). In Bianco et al. (1999), the authors design two constructive heuristics that outperform former work in the variant with precedence constraints. In Ferreira et al. (2021), the authors study the scheduling of Human-Robot teams as a specific case of the MMTSP. A GP algorithm and a Constraint

Programming model are proposed. Both methods present promising results for several instances of the problem.

None of these previous works took into account the stochastic aspect of real-world applications. In practice, unexpected events often interrupt the execution of planned schedules. Therefore, besides providing optimal and near-optimal solutions for deterministic settings, one must study methods for repairing the schedules under disruptions. This is particularly relevant in the current application as port management involves several machines and is subject to frequent disruptions (Pant et al., 2014). In such environments, the sequence of operations is dynamically adapted during the execution.

There are several strategies for dynamic scheduling. This work follows the classification from Aytug et al. (2005) that groups them into proactive, reactive and predictive-reactive approaches. Proactive approaches generate a robust schedule based on some prediction of the system behaviour. Xiong et al. (2013), for instance, propose a multi-objective evolutionary algorithm for generating robust schedules with minimum makespan. Surrogate models use the system information to measure the robustness of the solutions. Although these proactive methods have gained some research effort, their implementation is complex because the performance depends on the predictive information obtained.

Reactive approaches take no decision in advance. These strategies usually adopt fast and simple dispatching rules, which prioritise jobs for execution in real-time. Research on the performance of these rules has a long tradition, particularly in dynamic job shops. We refer to Haupt (1989) and Ramasesh (1990) for a comprehensive classification of them. They have been extensively adopted in dynamic manufacturing systems, where optimal schedules in a given moment quickly become sub-optimal. Effective dispatching rules have been developed for several scheduling problems, particularly in the semiconductor industry (Zhou et al., 2019). Xiong et al. (2017) design rules for a variant of the dynamic Job Shop Scheduling Problem in which jobs arrive in batch. Oukil and El-Bouri (2021) use DEA to classify several rules according to a multi-criteria objective in a dynamic flow-shop. In Su et al. (2017), authors address a dynamic parallel machine scheduling problem using a new composite rule. Recently, GP and other machine learning methods have been employed on the automated generation of rules with promising results (Nguyen et al., 2017; Jun et al., 2019; Ferreira et al., 2022).

This paper discusses the performance of predictive-reactive scheduling, an intermediate between the other two approaches, where a baseline schedule of the production system is adapted during the execution. Particularly, we examine the use of re-scheduling and dispatching rules combined with a predictive schedule. Ouelhadj and Petrovic (2008) classify re-scheduling strategies according to two criteria, *when-to-schedule* and *how-to-schedule*. Three approaches compose the first criteria: *periodic* re-scheduling, *event-driven* and *hybrid*. In the *periodic* policy, also known as *rolling horizon*, a schedule is completely generated at regular intervals, considering all available information. The problem is decomposed into several static problems and is usually solved by standard scheduling algorithms. *Event-driven* is the strategy of re-scheduling under unexpected events, such as a job arrival or delay. The *hybrid* policy is a composition of the *periodic* and *event-driven* approaches. In the *how-to-schedule* criterion, authors present two categories: *full scheduling*, in which all the jobs available are considered; and *partial scheduling*, which includes a percentage of the jobs or a part of the time horizon.

Sabuncuoğlu and Bayız (2000) developed a relevant study on re-scheduling strategies. They compare the performance of dispatching rules against the use of a beam search algorithm for partial scheduling through extensive computational experiments. The authors conclude that dispatching rules perform well in face of unexpected disruptions and that the performance of the partial scheduling approach improves as the frequency of re-scheduling increases. A classification of previous studies is also presented. In Sabuncuoğlu and Kizilisik (2003), the authors propose a simulation-optimisation algorithm for a dynamic Flexible Manufacturing System. Several strategies are tested considering the *when-to-schedule* and *how-to-schedule* criteria. The conclusion is the same as the previous study – the system’s performance gets better as the frequency of re-scheduling increases. Partial scheduling is particularly competitive when there are several machine breakdowns and low flexibility in the system.

Lou et al. (2012) combine robust scheduling with a reactive approach. The authors use a stochastic model to generate a predictive schedule and repair algorithms to adapt it when unexpected events occur. They show that the combination of both approaches generates more robust solutions than pure reactive methods. Liu and Zhou (2013) address parallel machines re-scheduling under job rework disruptions. Distinct conflicting criteria are considered in a bi-objective problem to minimise the completion time and the number of disrupted jobs. A polynomial-time algorithm is proposed to generate all efficient solutions in both criteria. In Yin et al. (2016), the authors face a bi-objective re-scheduling problem in deterministic parallel machines. A set of jobs must be re-scheduled to minimise both the mean completion time and the difference from the original schedule. The aim is to determine the set of Pareto-optimal solutions. They work with two variants of the problem (with fixed and variable number of machines) and show that both are NP-hard in the strong sense.

In a nutshell, the best way to deal with unexpected disruptions in scheduling depends on their frequency, nature (whether resource-related or job-related) and environment characteristics. Jain and Foley (2016) explore three approaches: no change in the original schedule, re-scheduling using heuristics, and switching to a completely reactive mode. Several methods are proposed and compared using simulation in manufacturing scenarios. The authors conclude that the proposed *Pairwise Exchange Heuristic* outperforms the other methods at low load level or shortest interruptions. The dispatching rules work better at high load levels and prolonged interruptions. The authors also highlight the relevance of avoiding modifications in the original schedule. They argue that the response to unexpected events needs to be surgical to avoid significant changes in promised delivery times.

Our work distinguishes from the above studies in three main aspects. Firstly, this is the only work addressing the optimisation of inbound operations in bulk ports. Despite the fact that some methods for scheduling multi-mode tasks have been proposed, none of them applies to the particularities of this application. Secondly, Jain and Foley (2016) employ a single interruption and measure the system behaviour for some hours after the interruption. We extend their work by exploring those strategies under uncertain processing times and using a stochastic simulation model. Third, none of the studies above evaluated their methods in large-sized practical instances. Several works are limited to 10 machines, while real application problems involve hundreds of machines as in bulk ports. Real scenarios from large ports are considered in our experiments, demonstrating the scalability and applicability of the proposed approaches.

3. The Wagon Unloading Problem

The problem concerns unloading trains to stockpiles. In this operation, the product is dumped from wagons and moved through the stockyard. We denote the set of all machines that transport the product from a wagon to a stockpile by route. A route starts at a car dumper, comprises several conveyor belts and ends at a stacker that piles up the material. Stackers are assigned to a location of the stockyard and reach only the stockpiles located there. A relevant aspect of the problem is that all machines in the route are used simultaneously during the unloading operation. To minimise the number of railway maneuvers, wagons are grouped into lots. Each lot has a set of eligible stockpiles – each route a small set of piles. Since each stockpile can be reached by a subset of routes, we can say that each lot has also a set of eligible routes. One must assign lots to routes and sequence them without overlap in every machine. The objective is to maximise the number of wagons unloaded in a given planning horizon.

Formally, let \mathcal{L} be the set of lots to be unloaded, \mathcal{M} be the set of machines and \mathcal{R} be the set of routes in the port. The machines of route $r \in \mathcal{R}$ are given by $\mathcal{M}_r \subset \mathcal{M}$. Each lot $l \in \mathcal{L}$ has a set of eligible routes $R_l \subset \mathcal{R}$, composed of all routes whose stacker reaches some pile eligible for l . The operation of lot l must start after its arrival time a_l . The processing time of lot l using route r is p_{lr} . We model this problem as an MMTSP, which is strongly NP-hard (Drozdowski, 2009). In the MMTSP, a set of tasks must be performed by machines. Each task must be assigned to an execution mode, and each mode is a subset of machines. In this work, the set of tasks is given by \mathcal{L} and each lot $l \in \mathcal{L}$ has a set of execution modes given by R_l .

To illustrate the problem description, Figure 1 illustrates a stockyard composed of four piles. At the bottom of the figure, a graph represents the routes – each node is a machine and arcs indicate the flow direction. In the example, \mathcal{L} is composed of two lots of five wagons each. Suppose that, given their product composition, only stockpiles 1 and 4 are eligible for these lots. They must be assigned to routes that end at stackers that reach those piles. Two possible routes are $CD1 - CB1 - CB4 - CB6 - S1$ and $CD3 - CB3 - CB4 - CB7 - S4$. As these routes share a machine (CB4), they cannot operate simultaneously.

To accommodate the specificities of the wagons unloading application, additional features are incorporated into the classical MMTSP:

- Railway maneuver – At the train arrival, an *initial maneuver* is performed to transport the lots to a buffer yard. The arrival time of lot l , a_l , includes the train arrival time plus the time for this maneuver. Just before starting any unloading operation, the *standard maneuver* takes the lot to the car dumper. During this maneuver, the car dumper must remain idle.
- Sequence-dependent setup times – Each machine is subject to a setup between two operations of distinct routes. If two subsequent operations use distinct routes that have at least one machine in common, a setup time must be inserted between those operations.
- Machines maintenance – Ports conduct frequently planned maintenance tasks, which take significant time from

Figure 1: The wagons unloading operation and the unloading routes.

the machines, and hence must be considered when scheduling them. During the maintenance time of some machine, no operation using that machine can be performed.

- Simultaneous use of machine – Some ports, as the ones from our case study, have conveyors and stackers with double the capacity of the car dumpers. These machines may be used simultaneously by two distinct lots if the two operations are directed to the same stockpile.

Figure 2 presents a Gantt chart of the car dumpers, where a schedule of eight lots and one maintenance task is given. Before each operation, a maneuver is executed. In general, setups are performed in parallel to the maneuvers. Exceptionally, the operation of lot 8 must wait for the finish of lot 5 and the setup of machine S3. In the example, machines CB4 and S2 have double capacity, which allows two lots simultaneously. That is the case of the lots in blue boxes (1 and 3, as well as 6 and 7). The lots in grey boxes are unloaded by dedicated routes.

In addition to the aforementioned extensions to the classical MMTSP, uncertainty in the processing times can be considered. In that case, the original schedule must be adapted during execution to accommodate deviations and maintain an effective throughput. However, before starting the unloading operation, lots must be transported to car dumpers via railway maneuvers. Changes on the baseline schedule lead to additional maneuvers and possibly

Figure 2: Feasible solution of the problem.

overhead in the number of resources required. To avoid this overhead, managers must find a good compromise between modifying the baseline and optimising the throughput. Therefore, the stochastic version of the problem aims at maximising the throughput, while minimising the number of deviations from the baseline schedule. Yin et al. (2016) measure schedule deviations as the difference from original jobs completion times. As our objective is to avoid railway maneuvers, we count the number of changes in car dumpers and in the sequence of lots. The number of deviations of lot l is given by the difference from its original to the new sequence. Moreover, if l is assigned to distinct car dumpers in each schedule, the number of deviations is incremented by one. If l changes the route but maintains the original car dumper and the sequence, no additional maneuver is necessary and no deviation is incurred.

4. Exact solution methods

This section describes the exact methods proposed to solve the deterministic version of the problem. At first, we introduce a Mixed Integer Programming (MIP) model, where the formulation proposed by Ferreira et al. (2021) to the MMTSP is adapted to the current application. Then we present the Constraint Programming model.

4.1. Mixed Integer Programming formulation

The problem is defined on a set of lots \mathcal{L} , machines \mathcal{M} and routes \mathcal{R} . We also define \mathcal{MT} , the set of planned maintenance tasks, and each task $j \in \mathcal{MT}$ is associated to a machine $m_j \in \mathcal{M}$. The parameters of the problem are summarised in Table 1. If m is a car dumper, the setup time $st_{r_1 r_2}^m$ corresponds to the standard maneuver time. Otherwise, $st_{r_1 r_2}^m$ applies only if $r_1 \neq r_2$.

Table 2 shows the variables of the model. To assist in the formulation, we define set $A_{l_1 r_1}$ composed of all pairs (l_2, r_2) eligible for simultaneous execution with (l_1, r_1) . In such case, l_1 and l_2 are eligible for at least one pile in common and this pile is reached by routes r_1 and r_2 . Moreover, $(l_2, r_2) \in A_{l_1 r_1}$ only if all machines in $\mathcal{M}_{r_1} \cap \mathcal{M}_{r_2}$ have double capacity. Variable $YP_{l_1 r_1 l_2 r_2}^m$ indicates that l_1 and l_2 share machine m and use routes r_1 and r_2 , respectively. By definition, if $(l_2, r_2) \notin A_{l_1 r_1}$ or if m is a single-capacity machine, $YP_{l_1 r_1 l_2 r_2}^m = 0$.

Table 1: Problem Parameters

Parameter	Description
at_l	Arrival time of lot l
p_{lr}	Processing time of lot l in route r
w_l	Number of wagons in lot l
$st_{r_1 r_2}^m$	Setup time of machine m from route r_1 to route r_2
sm_j	Start time of maintenance task j
fm_j	Finish time of maintenance task j
m_j	Machine associated to maintenance task j

Table 2: MIP Variables

Name	Description
Y_{lr}	1 if lot l is unloaded via route r ; 0 otherwise.
$X_{ml_1 l_2}$	1 if lots l_1 and l_2 use machine m and l_1 unloads before l_2 ; 0 otherwise.
$Y_{l_1 r_1 l_2 r_2}^m$	1 if lots l_1 and l_2 unload using routes r_1 and r_2 , respectively, and sharing machine m ; 0 otherwise.
XMB_{lj}	1 if lot l uses machine m_j before maintenance task j ; 0 otherwise.
XMA_{lj}	1 if lot l uses machine m_j after maintenance task j ; 0 otherwise.
N_{lr}	Number of wagons of lot l unloaded via route r before time reaches hz
S_{lr}	Start time of lot l in route r
F_{lr}	Finish time of lot l in route r
Z_{lr}	Minimum between F_{lr} and hz

In the MIP model, it is not mandatory to plan all lots. The objective function (1) aims at maximising the total number of wagons unloaded in the planning horizon hz . The parameter H is an upper bound for the maximum finish time of any planned lot, calculated as $hz + \hat{p}$, where $\hat{p} = \max_{l \in \mathcal{L}, r \in R_l} p_{lr}$. The model is given below.

$$\text{Max} \quad \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}} \sum_{r \in R_l} N_{lr} \quad (1)$$

Subject to:

$$\sum_{r \in R_l} Y_{lr} \leq 1 \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L} \quad (2)$$

$$F_{lr} \geq S_{lr} + p_{lr} - H \cdot (1 - Y_{lr}) \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r \in R_l \quad (3)$$

Constraints (2) ensure that each lot is assigned to at most one route and constraints (3) calculate the finish time of each lot according to its start time and assigned route.

$$\sum_{(l_2, r_2) \in A_{l_1 r_1}} YP_{l_1 r_1 l_2 r_2}^m \leq Y_{l_1 r_1} \quad \forall l_1 \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r_1 \in \mathcal{R}_{l_1}, \forall m \in \mathcal{M}_{r_1} \cup \mathcal{M}_{r_2} \quad (4)$$

$$YP_{l_1 r_1 l_2 r_2}^{m_1} = YP_{l_1 r_1 l_2 r_2}^{m_2} \quad \forall l_1 \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r_1 \in \mathcal{R}_{l_1}, \forall (l_2, r_2) \in A_{l_1 r_1}, \forall m_1, m_2 \in \mathcal{M}_{r_1} \cup \mathcal{M}_{r_2} \quad (5)$$

$$YP_{l_1 r_1 l_2 r_2}^m = YP_{l_2 r_2 l_1 r_1}^m \quad \forall l_1 \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r_1 \in \mathcal{R}_{l_1}, \forall (l_2, r_2) \in A_{l_1 r_1}, \forall m \in \mathcal{M}_{r_1} \cup \mathcal{M}_{r_2} \quad (6)$$

If m is a single-capacity machine, $YP_{l_1 r_1 l_2 r_2}^m = 0$ by definition. Constraints (4) guarantee that lot l_1 is planned to use route r_1 in a simultaneous operation only if its assigned to route r_1 in variable $Y_{l_1 r_1}$. Constraints (5) provide consistent planning for all machines used in simultaneous operations, and constraints (6) ensure consistency between variables $YP_{l_1 r_1 l_2 r_2}^m$ and $YP_{l_2 r_2 l_1 r_1}^m$.

$$S_{l_2 r_2} \geq F_{l_1 r_1} + st_{r_1 r_2}^m + H \cdot (Y_{l_1 r_1} + Y_{l_2 r_2} - YP_{l_1 r_1 l_2 r_2}^m + X_{ml_1 l_2} - 3) \quad \forall \langle l_1, r_1, l_2, r_2, m \rangle \in T \quad (7)$$

$$S_{l_1 r_1} \geq F_{l_2 r_2} + st_{r_2 r_1}^m + H \cdot (Y_{l_1 r_1} + Y_{l_2 r_2} - YP_{l_1 r_1 l_2 r_2}^m - X_{ml_1 l_2} - 2) \quad \forall \langle l_1, r_1, l_2, r_2, m \rangle \in T \quad (8)$$

The set T is composed of all tuples $\langle l_1, r_1, l_2, r_2, m \rangle$ in which r_1 is a route eligible for lot l_1 , r_2 is eligible for l_2 , and machine m is present both in r_1 and r_2 . Formally if $\langle l_1, r_1, l_2, r_2, m \rangle \in T$, $r_1 \in \mathcal{R}_{l_1}$, $r_2 \in \mathcal{R}_{l_2}$ and $m \in \mathcal{M}_{r_1} \cap \mathcal{M}_{r_2}$. Constraints (7) and (8) ensure that each single capacity machine will not process more than one lot at a time (these are the “no-overlap” constraints). If $YP_{l_1 r_1 l_2 r_2}^m = 1$, all double capacity machines in $\mathcal{M}_{r_1} \cap \mathcal{M}_{r_2}$ may overlap in the operation of l_1 and l_2 .

$$S_{lr} \geq at_l \cdot Y_{lr} \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_l \quad (9)$$

$$S_{lr} \leq hz \cdot Y_{lr} \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_l \quad (10)$$

$$Z_{lr} \leq F_{lr} \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_l \quad (11)$$

$$Z_{lr} \leq hz \cdot Y_{lr} \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_l \quad (12)$$

The start time of each lot is bounded by its arrival time in Constraints (9). The upper bound of any start time is given by the planning horizon in Constraints (10). Constraints (11) and (12) ensure that Z_{lr} is the minimum between the finish time of each lot and the planning horizon hz , or 0 if lot l is not assigned to route r .

$$N_{lr} \leq \frac{w_l}{p_{lr}} \cdot (Z_{lr} - S_{lr}) \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_l \quad (13)$$

Constraints (13) calculate the number of wagons unloaded, which depends on the time taken from S_{lr} and Z_{lr} (the operation time inside the planning horizon).

$$Y_{lr} \leq XMB_{lj} + XMA_{lj} \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{MT}, \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_l : m_j \in \mathcal{M}_r \quad (14)$$

$$sm_j \geq F_{lr} + H \cdot (Y_{lr} + XMB_{lj} - 2) \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{MT}, \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_l : m_j \in \mathcal{M}_r \quad (15)$$

$$S_{lr} \geq fm_j + H \cdot (Y_{lr} + XMA_{lj} - 2) \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{MT}, \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_l : m_j \in \mathcal{M}_r \quad (16)$$

If machine m_j is used in the operation of lot l , variables XMB_{lj} and XMA_{lj} define if the operation is performed before task j . If $Y_{lr} = XMB_{lj} = 1$, constraints (15) ensure that lot l is unloaded before j . Otherwise, if $Y_{lr} = XMA_{lj} = 1$, constraints (16) ensure that task j is executed before lot l .

$$Y_{lr} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_l \quad (17)$$

$$X_{ml_1l_2} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall l_1, \forall l_2 \in \mathcal{L}, \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (18)$$

$$YP_{l_1r_1l_2r_2}^m \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall l_1, l_2 \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r_1 \in \mathcal{R}_{l_1}, \forall r_2 \in \mathcal{R}_{l_2}, \forall m \in \mathcal{M}_{r_1} \cup \mathcal{M}_{r_2} \quad (19)$$

$$XMB_{lj}, XMA_{lj} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{MT}, \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_l : m_j \in \mathcal{M}_r \quad (20)$$

$$N_{lr} \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_l \quad (21)$$

$$S_{lr}, F_{lr}, Z_{lr} \geq 0 \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_l \quad (22)$$

Constraints (17) to (22) define the domain of the variables.

4.2. Constraint Programming model

Constraint Programming (CP) has been recently applied in complex scheduling problems (Gökgür et al., 2018; Åstrand et al., 2020; Lunardi et al., 2020). The approach is particularly effective in problems with a high number of constraints limiting the search space. In Ferreira et al. (2021), a CP model is designed for the MMTSP. The algorithm outperforms existing heuristics and motivates the development of a specific model for the current application. An overview of Constraint Programming applied to scheduling problems is found in Baptiste et al. (2001).

CP algorithms solve a Constraint Satisfaction Problem (CSP), composed of variables with a finite set of domain values. Constraints limit the combination of values that the variables set may assume. A feasible solution of a CSP is an assignment of variables to values that satisfy all constraints (Tsang, 1993). CP algorithms generally have two phases. In the first, constraint propagation procedures filter the variables domain and reduce the search space. Then, an exhaustive search throughout the reduced search space is performed. When solving optimisation problems, the CSP has an objective function f and aims at finding the solution S^* that satisfies the CSP and optimises f . If the algorithm completes the search by enumerating all feasible solutions, S^* is the optimal solution to the problem.

Our CP model solves the problem described in Section 3. Table 3 presents the variables set. Interval variables represent the period of time of operations, from start to finish. We define four types of interval variables, as shown in the table: L_l , LR_{lr} , $Par_{l_1r_1l_2r_2}$ and $Par2_{l_1r_1l_2r_2}$. Variable L_l model the start and finish time of lot $l \in \mathcal{L}$. If l_1 unloads by

the dedicated route r_1 , the value of L_{l_1} is given by variable $LR_{l_1r_1}$. Otherwise, if l_1 unloads in a simultaneous operation with lot l_2 , the value of L_{l_1} is given by variable $Par_{l_1r_1l_2r_2}$, where r_1 and r_2 are the double-capacity routes involved. In such case, it is not mandatory that lots l_1 and l_2 start and finish at the exact same time. If lot l_1 starts earlier than l_2 , for instance, the start time of $Par_{l_1r_1l_2r_2}$ is earlier than the start time of $Par_{l_2r_2l_1r_1}$. Variable $Par_{l_1r_1l_2r_2}$ represents the whole interval in which both lots operate.

Table 3: Variables of the Constraint Programming model

Variable	Type	Description
L_l	Interval	Time of lot l unloading
LR_{lr}	Interval	Time of l unloading using route r
$Par_{l_1r_1l_2r_2}$	Interval	Time of l_1 unloading using r_1 in parallel to l_2 unloading using r_2
$Par_{l_2r_2l_1r_1}$	Interval	Time of both lots l_1 and l_2 unloading using routes r_1 and r_2 in parallel
E_l	Integer	Minimum between the finish time of lot l and hz
W_{lr}	Integer	Number of wagons from lot l unloaded via route r
Seq_m	Sequence	Sequence of operations of machine m

For each machine $m \in \mathcal{M}$, a sequence variable Seq_m is defined. The value of each variable Seq_m is the order in which machine m executes its operations. Thus, Seq_m is defined on the set of interval variables that involve route $r : m \in \mathcal{M}_r$. The objective of this variable is to set the value of each variable LR_{lr} and $Par_{l_1r_1l_2r_2}$ without overlap in the use of machine m .

The model is described below. Functions $start_of(X)$ and $end_of(X)$ return, respectively, the start and finish time of each interval variable X . The objective function (23) is to maximise the number of wagons unloaded before the end of the planning horizon hz .

$$\text{Max} \quad \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}, r \in \mathcal{R}} W_{lr} \quad (23)$$

$$\text{alternative}(L_l, LR_{lr} | r \in \mathcal{R}_l \cup Par_{lr_1l_2r_2} | r \in \mathcal{R}_l, < l_2, r_2 > \in A_{lr}) \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L} \quad (24)$$

$$\text{presence_of}(Par_{lr_1l_2r_2}) \Rightarrow \text{presence_of}(Par_{l_2r_2lr}) \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_l, \forall < l_2, r_2 > \in A_{lr} \quad (25)$$

The function $alternative()$ in Constraints (24) sets the value of L_l equals to one of the variables LR_{lr} or $Par_{lr_1l_2r_2}$. A route r must be selected for lot l . If r is used in dedicated mode, $L_l = LR_{lr}$. Otherwise, l unloads in parallel to lot l_2 using route r_2 and $L_l = Par_{lr_1l_2r_2}$. Constraints(25) ensure consistency between variables $Par_{lr_1l_2r_2}$ and $Par_{l_2r_2lr}$.

$$start_of(L_l) \geq at_l \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L} \quad (26)$$

$$E_l = \min(hz, end_of(L_l)) \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L} \quad (27)$$

$$presence_of(LR_{lr}) \Rightarrow W_{lr} = (start_of(LR_{lr}) - E_l) \cdot \frac{w_l}{p_{lr}} \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_l \quad (28)$$

$$presence_of(Par_{lr_1l_2r_2}) \Rightarrow W_{lr} = (start_of(Par_{lr_1l_2r_2}) - E_l) \cdot \frac{w_l}{p_{lr}} \quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_l, \forall \langle l_2, r_2 \rangle \in A_{lr_1} \quad (29)$$

Constraints (26) ensure that l unloads after its arrival time. Constraints (27) calculate the value of E_l , which is the minimum between hz and the finish time of lot l . This is necessary to calculate the number of wagons unloaded before hz . In constraints (28), the number of wagons W_{lr} is calculated from variable LR_{lr} and in constraints (29), variable $Par_{lr_1l_2r_2}$ defines the number of wagons.

$$start_of(LR_{lr}) \geq fm_j \parallel end_of(LR_{lr}) \leq sm_j \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{MT}, \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_l \cap \mathcal{R}_{m_j} \quad (30)$$

$$start_of(Par_{l_1r_1l_2r_2}) \geq fm_j \parallel end_of(Par_{l_1r_1l_2r_2}) \leq sm_j \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{MT}, \forall l_1 \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r_1 \in \mathcal{R}_l \cap \mathcal{R}_{m_j}, \forall \langle l_2, r_2 \rangle \in A_{l_1r_1} \quad (31)$$

Constraints (30) and (31) ensure that the unloading operation of each lot is scheduled before the start or after the finish of each task $j \in \mathcal{MT}$. We define $\mathcal{R}_m \subset \mathcal{R}$ as the subset of routes composed of machine m . Given machine m and lot l , the subset $\mathcal{R}_l \cap \mathcal{R}_m$ is composed of all routes that include machine m and are eligible for lot l .

$$start_of(Par2_{l_1r_1l_2r_2}) \leq start_of(Par_{l_1r_1l_2r_2}) \quad \forall l_1 \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r_1 \in \mathcal{R}_{l_1}, \forall \langle l_2, r_2 \rangle \in A_{l_1r_1} \quad (32)$$

$$end_of(Par2_{l_1r_1l_2r_2}) \geq end_of(Par_{l_1r_1l_2r_2}) \quad \forall l_1 \in \mathcal{L}, \forall r_1 \in \mathcal{R}_{l_1}, \forall \langle l_2, r_2 \rangle \in A_{l_1r_1} \quad (33)$$

Variables $Par2_{l_1r_1l_2r_2}$ represent the whole interval when lots l_1 and l_2 uses routes r_1 and r_2 if they operate simultaneously. Constraints (32) and (33) calculate the start and finish of $Par2_{l_1r_1l_2r_2}$, respectively.

$$no_overlap(Seq_m, st_{r_1r_2}^m \quad \forall r_1, r_2 \in \mathcal{R}) \quad \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (34)$$

In a feasible solution, each single-capacity machine $m \in \mathcal{M}$ can process at most one lot and each double-capacity machine operates at most two lots simultaneously. This is guaranteed by constraints (34). By associating variables $LR_{lr} : m \in \mathcal{M}_r$ to the sequence variable Seq_m we impose that no operation in dedicated mode is executed with overlap in machine m . Similarly, if m is a double-capacity machine, we associate variables $Par2_{l_1r_1l_2r_2} : m \in \mathcal{M}_{r_1} \cap \mathcal{M}_{r_2}$ to Seq_m . Thus, operations of lots l_1 and l_2 can overlap in the use of machine m , but no other operation can overlap them. The function `no_overlap()` also accepts the definition of setup times $st_{r_1r_2}^m$ between each pair of operations.

As the constraint programming solvers do not scale well for larger-sized instances, an heuristic approach is also provided. The following section details the GP algorithm developed in this work.

5. GP-based solution methods

Genetic Programming has been successfully applied as a hyper-heuristic on the design of new heuristics for scheduling problems (Nguyen et al., 2017). Similarly to Genetic Algorithms (GA), GP is an evolutionary and population approach. However, GP manipulates symbolic expressions rather than arrays of numbers or other rigid structures. Therefore, GP is more powerful to create heuristics to a problem..

This work applies GP for two purposes. First, for the deterministic version of the problem, we apply a greedy-randomised heuristic (GRH), which uses GP-evolved rules to select operations to create the schedule. Then we use GP for evolving dispatching rules for the stochastic version. They are used as reactive methods, to select the next operation to be executed once a machine is idle. The GRH heuristic and the specific GP algorithm developed in this work are described in the next sections.

5.1. Greedy-randomised heuristic

The premise of the GRH algorithm is that no single rule performs best in all instances. Thus, many rules are applied for prioritising operations and generating schedules. However, instead of always selecting the best priority, GRH employs a greedy-randomised approach. The pseudo-code is provided in Algorithm 1, which receives as input an instance i and a set of priority rules R . Until reaching a stopping criterion, GRH uses each rule $pr \in R$ for a given number of consecutive iterations ($max_iterations_{pr}$) in turn. At each iteration, a complete schedule S is generated (line 10). The general idea is to adapt the value of $max_iterations_{pr}$ to the performance of pr on instance i and let the best-performing rules run for more iterations. Hence, at the beginning of the algorithm, all rules receive the same number of iterations (line 2). Every time pr finds a new incumbent solution S (throughput τ_S being the best found so far), the value of $max_iterations_{pr}$ is increment by 1 (lines 11-13). The stopping criterion is reaching a given number of total iterations.

The procedure *greedy_randomised_schedule_generation* in line 10 starts with an empty schedule. Once a machine is available, rule r is applied to select the next pair <lot, route> and insert it in the schedule. Instead of selecting the pair <lot, route> with the best score, a list of candidates is created, containing the best $\alpha\%$ pairs available for execution. Then, the next pair to be executed is randomly selected from the candidate list. Hence, the parameter α indicates the algorithm's greediness (if $\alpha = 1$, a completely random approach is performed). When inserting a new operation using route r in the schedule, the starting time is the earliest time when all machines in r are available.

5.2. Genetic Programming

In the deterministic version of the problem, the search power of GP leverages GHR's performance by providing effective rules. In the stochastic case, GP evolves dispatching rules for sequencing the operations in a completely reactive approach. This section describes the specific GP developed in this work, applied in both versions of the Wagon Unloading Problem, which differ on their objectives. In the deterministic case, GP aims to find rules that

Algorithm 1: Greedy-randomised constructive algorithm

Input: Instance i , priority rules R , greed factor α

Result: Best solution found S^*

```
1 foreach priority rule  $pr \in R$  do
2   |  $max\_iterations_{pr} \leftarrow 1$ ;
3  $S^* \leftarrow \emptyset$ ;
4  $pr \leftarrow first\_rule$ ;
5  $iter \leftarrow 0$ ;
6 while not reached stopping criterion do
7   | if  $iter = max\_iterations_{pr}$  then
8     |    $pr \leftarrow next\_rule$ ;
9     |    $iter \leftarrow 0$ ;
10   $S \leftarrow greedy\_randomised\_schedule\_generation(\alpha, pr, i)$ ;
11  if  $\tau_S > \tau_{S^*}$  then
12    |    $S^* \leftarrow S$ ;
13    |    $max\_iterations_{pr} \leftarrow max\_iteration_{pr} + 1$ ;
14   $iter \leftarrow iter + 1$ ;
```

maximise the throughput. In the version with stochastic processing times, the aim is also to minimise deviations from a baseline schedule.

Figure 3 illustrates the general procedure of GP algorithms, which basically comprises a training and a validation stage. During training, the algorithm starts with a randomly created population and evolve it over several generations. Each individual a is evaluated by running a simulator of the scheduling environment on a set of training instances. In the evaluation of a , the corresponding rule is applied by the simulator. Then a fitness score is assigned to a representing its overall performance on the training set. The best individuals are reproduced and combined by the genetic operators, crossover and mutation. The crossover operator selects two nodes from distinct individuals and swaps the sub-trees rooted by those nodes. Mutation selects a node from any individual tree and replaces the sub-tree rooted by that node with a randomly generated tree. Both genetic operators use tournament on the selection of individuals. Once reaching a stopping criterion, the training stage finishes, and the best individual found is evaluated on the validation instance set. The pseudo-code of the GP algorithm is found in Section A from Appendix.

Figure 3 also presents an example of an individual and its corresponding rule. The most common representation are symbolic expression trees, whose leaf nodes are *terminals* related to the specific problem. The internal nodes are *functions* that operate the terminals. In the GP designed in this work, each tree, a , represents a (priority or dispatching) rule whose terminals are parameters from the lots and machines. In the figure, individual a is composed

Figure 3: The two stages of GP algorithm (training and validation) and example of a GP individual tree

of the terminals 2, F (finish time of operation) and W (number of wagons). The mathematical operators $-$ and $*$ compose the function set. By decoding a , rule $F - 2W$ is obtained.

In the simulation model, there is a single queue for all lots arriving at the buffer yard. Given the interdependencies of the assignment and sequence decisions, they are taken together. Thus, the rule selects the next lot for unloading and the route at the same time. Once at least one route is available, rule r assigns scores for each pair $\langle \text{lot}, \text{route} \rangle$. The procedure goes on until all lots are executed. In the stochastic version of the problem, actual processing times p_{lr} are uncertain and sampled from a Gamma distribution (Lawrence and Sewell, 1997). The coefficient of variation of the distribution (cv) is an instance parameter.

5.2.1. Fitness calculation

The fitness function computes the performance of each individual a on a training set of instances. The simulation procedure applies rule r on each instance i , and returns the throughput τ_{ai} , measured as the percentage of wagons unloaded in the planning horizon hz . The average throughput of a in the training set is given by τ_a . In the stochastic version, we aim to find rules that maximise the throughput and minimise deviations from the baseline schedule. Thus, the performance of rule r also depends on dev_a , the average number of deviations from the baseline per lot. Section 3 explains how we calculate the number of deviations from the baseline. As throughput and number of deviations have different unit measures, a factor δ is applied to the latter. The performance of individual a is estimated as $\tau_a + dev_a \cdot \delta$. When running GP for the deterministic version, $\delta = 0$ and only τ_a accounts in individuals performance.

GP trees tend to grow during the search and result in complex rules, an effect known as bloat. Several strategies may be applied to avoid this effect. In our case, the tree size is penalised in the fitness function according to ρ , the bloat control factor. The penalty of tree size depends on the number of nodes $|a|$, the number of generations completed g and the value of ρ . Hence, in addition to the rules' performance, the fitness function also considers a strategy to avoid large trees, as in Equation 35.

$$fitness(a, g) = \tau_a + dev_a \cdot \delta + |a| \cdot g \cdot \rho \quad (35)$$

5.2.2. Functions and terminal set

The function set is composed of the four basic mathematical operations: sum (+), subtraction (/), multiplication (*) and the protected division (/), which returns one if the denominator is zero. Table 4 shows the terminal set, composed of parameters from the lots and the machines. Terminal F returns the finish time of the current operation if it starts next, considering maneuver and eventual machines' maintenance. Five terminals refer to eligibility, which by definition vary from 0 to 1. The eligibility of lot l is calculated as R_l/\mathcal{R} (terminal LE). The route eligibility (RE) is the percentage of lots eligible for the route, considering all remaining lots. Terminal REAv returns the route eligibility considering only lots available at the current simulation time. Terminals CE and CEAv are similar to RE and REAv, but referring to car dumpers. DCap indicates if some machine in the route has double capacity. Finally, terminal DEV returns the number of deviations from baseline incurred if the current pair <lot, route> is selected. It applies only to the stochastic case.

Table 4: Terminal set of the GP algorithms

Terminal	Description
PT	Operation processing time
F	Operation finish time
W	Number of wagons on the lot
LE	Lot eligibility
RE	Route eligibility on all remaining lots
REAv	Route eligibility on available lots
CE	Car dumper eligibility on all remaining lots
CEAv	Car dumper eligibility on available lots
DCap	1 if route has double capacity, 0 otherwise
DEV	Deviations from baseline

6. Experiments design

We evaluate the proposed methods in real and fictitious ports. This section explain the instance generation and the design of the experiments. We also describe the parameters setting of the algorithms.

6.1. Instances

The computational experiments use three instance classes. The first two refers to real ports from Vale, and the third comprises fictitious ports. Table 5 shows data from each of the real ports and the randomly generated instances. The value of all time-related parameters is presented in minutes. All instances have a planning horizon of one day ($hz = 1440$ minutes).

Vale is the worldwide leader in iron ore production in terms of volume (Comtois and Slack, 2016). Three production systems in Brazil export the iron ore overseas for steel companies. Our case study is based on two ports from Vale that appear in the top five iron ore terminals (Merk and Dang, 2012). This work name them as LargePort and ComplexPort. Among both ports, LargePort is the largest in the number of machines and volume, but the operation of ComplexPort is more complex. In this port, lots have a limited number of eligible piles. Thus, it is challenging to keep all car dumpers operating without conflict in routes. LargePort has four stackers with double capacity, and ComplexPort has three. In the instances considered in this work, both ports have a 24 hours maintenance task for one car dumper, and two stackers have 4-5 hours of maintenance.

Table 5: Instances from real ports and randomly generated ports

	LargePort	ComplexPort	General instances
Setup time	15	20	15
Standard maneuver time	55	20	30
time	55	75	30
Number of car dumpers (cds)	8	5	3 to 7
Number of stackers	12	10	3 to 7
Number of conveyors	133	193	3 to 7
Number of routes	544	1453	7 to 54
Number of products	14	74	2 to 20
Avg. number of of piles	155.5	96.0	20.0
Avg. number of piles/lot	30.4	1.5	1.0 to 10.0
Standard number of wagons/lot (w)	110	86	100
Avg.number of lots/train (lt)	3	3	1
Avg. processing time (\bar{p})	137.4	81.2	75.0

The third class of instances (general instances) include 24 fictitious ports, each with a specific number of machines and products. The aim is to validate the methods in a wide spectrum of ports beyond the large real iron ports. The number of machines and routes is smaller than in the real ports to represent simpler operations. Some parameters such as setup time, maneuver times, and the number of wagons per lot do not vary because preliminary experiments concluded that they do not significantly influence the overall output. Processing times are sampled from $U(50, 100)$. The number of products varies from 2 to 20, and we assume that all ports have 20 piles. Each pile and each lot are assigned to one of the products using a uniform distribution. Thus, in ports with larger number of products, each lot has a smaller number of eligible piles. This is relevant because it influences the overall flexibility of the unloading operations. See Section B from Appendix for a detailed presentation of each of the fictitious ports.

In the three instance classes, we generate fictitious trains at random considering the characteristics of each port: the standard number of wagons per lot, the average number of lots per train and the average number of eligible piles per lot. Arrivals are sampled from a Poisson distribution which mean λ is calculated as follows:

$$\lambda = \frac{u \cdot cds}{\bar{p} \cdot lt},$$

where cds is the number of car dumpers in the port and \bar{p} is the average processing time. As λ refers to train arrivals, we multiply \bar{p} by the average number of lots per train, lt . From queuing theory, the parameter u is an upper bound for the car dumpers utilisation. To incorporate realistic characteristics to the trains, not all lots have the same number of wagons. 90% of them have the standard number of wagons (w); 9% of them are divided into two lots of $w/2$ wagons, and 1% of them into three lots containing $w/2$, $w/4$ and $w/4$ wagons.

Table 6 presents the instance sets used by the GP algorithm for training and validation. The latter is also used for evaluating the MIP model and the CP algorithm. The aim is to simulate distinct scenarios, from days with a limited number of train arrivals to extremely congested ones. Thus, we adopt six values for u during validation. During training, we do not consider the extreme values (0.4 and 1.4). We use 6 fictitious port 6 for training and 18 for validation. The coefficient of variation cv defines the uncertainty level in processing times. The actual processing times are sampled from a gamma distribution with mean $\mathbb{E}[p_{lr}]$ and standard deviation $\sigma_{lr} = \mathbb{E}[p_{lr}] \cdot cv$. The higher the value of cv , the higher the uncertainty level. Five levels of cv are simulated when evaluating strategies for responding to schedule disruptions. In the deterministic version, $cv = 0$. For each combination of u , cv and port, we generate 10 distinct instances for training and 20 for validation (there is no intersection in both sets). The total number of instances result from the full-factorial design of all these parameters.

Table 6: GP training and validation sets

	Training set	Validation set	
Machines utilisation (u)	0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2	0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4	
Number of fictitious ports	6	18	
Deterministic	Variation in processing times (cv)	0	
	# Instances from LargePort	$4 \cdot 1 \cdot 10 = 40$	$6 \cdot 1 \cdot 20 = 120$
	# Instances from ComplexPort	$4 \cdot 1 \cdot 10 = 40$	$6 \cdot 1 \cdot 20 = 120$
	# General instances	$4 \cdot 6 \cdot 10 = 240$	$6 \cdot 18 \cdot 20 = 2160$
Stochastic	Variation in processing times (cv)	0.4, 0.8	0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0
	# Instances from LargePort	$4 \cdot 1 \cdot 2 \cdot 10 = 80$	$6 \cdot 1 \cdot 5 \cdot 20 = 600$
	# Instances from ComplexPort	$4 \cdot 1 \cdot 2 \cdot 10 = 80$	$6 \cdot 1 \cdot 5 \cdot 20 = 600$
	# General instances	$4 \cdot 6 \cdot 2 \cdot 10 = 480$	$6 \cdot 18 \cdot 5 \cdot 20 = 10800$

6.2. Algorithms parameters

Table 7 summarises the algorithm parameters adopted after preliminary experiments. The mutation probability is high, 0.8, as it effectively provides diversity in the algorithm search. Conversely, if crossover probability or tournament size is high, the evolution tends to stagnate too early with a homogeneous population. Thus, crossover probability is set to 0.2 and the tournament size to the minimum value, 2. We set the maximum depth of trees to the standard value of 17 for avoiding premature prune of good branches. The probability of selecting a terminal and a non-terminal (0.1 and 0.9, respectively) and the parameters of the Ramped Half-and-Half algorithm (minimum tree depth of 2 and maximum 6) are also set to standard values.

In order to tune the bloat control strategy, we ran 10 executions of GP for each value of $\rho = \{10^{-4}, 10^{-5}, 10^{-6}, 0\}$. We observed that ρ is effective for bloat control and helps to find smaller rules. In the instances from ComplexPort, for instance, the average size of the rules is 1, 7.4, 29.22 and 88.2 for $\rho = \{10^{-4}, 10^{-5}, 10^{-6}, 0\}$, respectively. However, no difference in performance was found when using $\rho = \{10^{-5}, 10^{-6}, 0\}$. For $\rho = 10^{-4}$, the algorithm results in worse-performing rules. Similar results are found in the other two instance classes. Thus, we consider that there is a good balance between bloat control and rules performance with $\rho = 10^{-5}$. We perform extensive GP runs using four values of δ . Results are discussed in Section 7.1. The greediness of the GRH algorithm decreases as α increases. In 10 experiments using distinct values (0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.5), the average solution quality is better with $\alpha = 0.2$. The algorithm presents no solution improvement after 400 iterations. Thus, we set its stopping criterion as completing 500 total iterations.

Table 7: GP Parameters Setting

Algorithm	Parameter	Adopted values
GP	Population size	800
	Number of generations	100
	Tournament size	2
	Maximum tree depth	17
	Crossover probability	0.2
	Mutation probability	0.8
	Bloat control factor (ρ)	10^{-5}
	Deviation penalty (δ)	0, 0.01, 0.1, 1
GRH	Greed factor (α)	0.2
	Total number of iterations	500

7. Experiments results

This section describes the performance comparison of the proposed methods in the validation sets described in Section 6.1. We start by explaining the rules obtained via GP. Then we present the results on the deterministic version of the problem. Finally, we explore the performance of seven strategies in responding to disruptions in the planned schedule. All methods were coded in Java and ran on Intel(R) Xeon(R) Processor E5 Family CPU with 2.8 GHz of speed using up to 48 GB of RAM. The GP algorithm uses the evolutionary computation library ECJ (Luke, 2017). The Mixed Integer Programming and Constraint Programming models use commercial solvers, respectively, ILOG CPLEX and ILOG CP Optimizer (both in version 20.10).

7.1. Evolved rules

In the generation of the priority rules, 30 independent GP runs were performed for each instance class. The rules obtained are compared by running the simulator on the validation set (deterministic version). In the instances from real ports, the performance of the rules is quite homogeneous – in LargePort, the evolved rules' average throughput (τ_a) varies from 82.7% to 83.5% and in ComplexPort from 67.1% to 67.9%. The experiments on the randomly generated ports resulted in only three distinct rules with average performances of 76.9%, 76.4% and 74.6%.

Table 8 presents three evolved rules in each instance class and their average throughput. As in LargePort and ComplexPort the rules have low variance in the average performance, we selected three with distinct behaviour on individual instances. The majority of the rules is compact and may be easily interpreted. Two terminals are frequently used, F (finish time of operation) and W (the number of wagons). The use of these terminals prioritises operations that finish earlier and lots with a larger number of wagons. We also observe that the rules of the general instances are

quite short and simple, possibly because the machines and routes of the fictitious ports are quite uniform. Thus, GP cannot find relevant parameters for prioritising lots there.

Table 8: Priority rules evolved for the deterministic problem

Instance class	Expression	Throughput (τ_a)
LargePort	$F - (PT/LE) + (DCap+LE) \cdot RE \cdot CEAv$	83.5%
	$F - W^2 \cdot RE \cdot CDE^2$	83.3%
	$F + RE - (DCap + PT) \cdot PT + REAv / (DCap - RE)$	82.7%
ComplexPort	$F \cdot CEAv / W$	67.9%
	$LE / (PT - F) - RE$	67.8%
	$DCap + F \cdot CDEAv - W$	67.2%
General	$F - W$	76.9%
	F	76.4%
	F/W	74.6%

In the stochastic case, each simulation has a baseline schedule – the best-known deterministic solution found one of the proposed methods. The objective is to design dispatching rules that maximise the throughput with minimum deviations from the baseline. Thus, the performance of each rule is measured by $\tau_a + dev_a \cdot \delta$, where dev_a is the average number of deviations per lot and δ is a parameter used to balance the value of τ_a and dev_a . The larger the value of δ , the highest the penalty for deviations from the baseline. We considered four values of δ : 0, 0.01, 0.1 and 1, and ran 30 independent executions of GP for each value, obtaining 120 rules for each instance class.

The charts of Figure 4 show the performance of the rules obtained for LargePort and ComplexPort, grouped by the value of δ used during training. When $\delta = 0$, not only the average deviation produced by the rules is much higher than in the other cases, but also the throughput is not noticeably higher (on the contrary). Therefore, using this parameter is important. There is also a large difference in the number of deviations produced in each port. The reason is the limited number of alternative routes for each lot in ComplexPort; several changes in car dumpers and sequences are necessary to effectively accommodate the schedule to disruptions. Moreover, in ComplexPort, penalising the deviation does not affect the average throughput obtained. Indeed, it seems that δ somehow guides the algorithm search to better rules, possibly because these rules tend to reproduce the priority of lots of the original schedule.

The selected dispatching rules are presented in Table 9. For each instance class, we took the rule that produced the best throughput and the one with minimum deviation from the baseline. The aim is to analyse the trade-off between both objectives. Thus, two rules are selected for LargePort and the General instances. In ComplexPort, a single rule dominates the others in both criteria. As expected, all rules present the terminal DEV, which measures the number of deviations per lot. Observe that in the rules DR_LP1, DR_CP and DR_1 (fewer number of deviations), the value of

Figure 4: Thought and number of deviations resulted from the evolved rules. Independent runs were performed using distinct penalties for deviations.

DEV has a large influence on the score. On the contrary, in rules DR_LP2 and DR_2, DEV is unlikely to determine the rule’s behaviour, as it assumes values much smaller than F.

Table 9: Dispatching rules generated for the stochastic problem

Instance class	Rule	Expression	Throughput (τ_a)	Deviations per lot (dev_a)
LargePort	DR_LP1	$1 + DCap + (DEV - RE)/CDEAv$	79.5%	1.06
LargePort	DR_LP2	$DEV + DCap/RE + CDE + F - RE$	80.6%	1.53
ComplexPort	DR_CP	$LE \cdot F / (DEV \cdot RE) + CDE - RE - DCap/LE + DEV \cdot F^2$	66.9%	1.43
General	DR_1	$F \cdot (DEV + LE)$	75.4%	0.93
General	DR_2	$(DEV + F)/W$	76.2%	1.59

7.2. Deterministic settings

This section reports the performance of the MIP model, the CP algorithm and the GP combined with GRH. The first two received a time limit of one hour for execution. Table 10 summarises the results, grouping instances by the parameter u . The average number of lots, which depends on u , is also reported. Column “GP + GRH” refers to the average of 20 runs of GRH for each instance. Columns “# Instances” present the number of instances for which each

method provided feasible solutions. Due to the size of the instances from the real ports, the MIP model did not obtain any integer solution for them. For the same reason, the CP model found solutions for only 93 out of the 240 instances from these ports. As MIP and CP did not find solutions for some instances, the values in column “Throughput” cannot be directly compared in all cases.

Instances from LargePort result in an average throughput much higher than the ones from ComplexPort, 87.2% on average against 73.4%. This is possibly due to the large number of eligible routes per lot in LargePort. In all instance sets, the throughput tends to decrease as the number of lots increases. This is expected since the throughput is relative to the number of lots, and the number of machines does not vary with u . The MIP model found the optimal solution of 60 instances, but its average performance is far from the other two methods. In general, CP is outperformed by GP+GRH, which also provides a considerable shorter computational time. Analysing only the instances with solutions found by CP, GP+GRH is better in LargePort and the general instances, producing an increased throughput of 2.2% and 2.9% pp when compared to CP, respectively. In ComplexPort, both methods are roughly equivalent.

Table 10: Performance of the proposed approaches on deterministic instances

Instance class	u	#Lots	MIP			CP			GP + GRH		
			#Instances	Throughput	Time (s)	#Instances	Throughput	Time (s)	#Instances	Throughput	Time (s)
LargePort	0.4	20.3	0	-	-	20	93.7%	2233	20	94.6%	3.8
	0.6	29.9	0	-	-	14	87.8%	3145	20	91.2%	6.1
	0.8	42.0	0	-	-	5	87.6%	3020	20	87.9%	11.6
	1	45.3	0	-	-	1	100.0%	346	20	85.3%	20.7
	1.2	57.2	0	-	-	0	-	-	20	81.7%	32.3
	1.4	67.8	0	-	-	0	-	-	20	75.4%	38.2
	Total/Average			0	-	-	40	91.0%	2603	120	86.0%
ComplexPort	0.4	29.3	0	-	-	19	82.0%	3418	20	81.4%	0.3
	0.6	38.4	0	-	-	19	82.8%	3318	20	81.5%	0.5
	0.8	50.7	0	-	-	13	75.0%	3610	20	75.0%	1.3
	1	67.8	0	-	-	2	61.4%	3622	20	67.5%	2.6
	1.2	74.4	0	-	-	0	-	-	20	63.3%	3.2
	1.4	88.6	0	-	-	0	-	-	20	55.4%	5.4
	Total/Average			0	-	-	53	79.8%	3373	120	70.7%
General	0.4	28.7	345	78.2%	3141	360	92.2%	3335	360	92.1%	0.3
	0.6	43.3	319	61.4%	3439	360	89.3%	3486	360	89.6%	0.7
	0.8	58.9	254	42.9%	3073	360	83.1%	3583	360	84.8%	1.7
	1	74.0	155	36.7%	3362	360	72.8%	3604	360	76.4%	3.1
	1.2	88.7	129	34.7%	3672	360	61.2%	3606	360	67.6%	5.0
	1.4	104.4	132	28.0%	3811	360	52.5%	3606	360	58.2%	6.3
	Total/Average			1334	47.0%	3416	2160	75.2%	3537	2160	78.1%

As CP does not scale well to larger instances, its relative performance is better in instances with a limited number of lots. On the other hand, the method presents a competitive performance ComplexPort – where it is difficult to avoid conflicts due to the large number of products. In instances of ComplexPort with $u \leq 0.6$, CP provides an average throughput 0.5% p.p better. In the class of general instances with $u \leq 0.6$, CP and GP are quite similar (90.9% against 90.8%, respectively). For $u > 0.6$, GP+GRH is much better than CP: the heuristic generate solutions with an average throughput of 71.8%, while CP results in 67.4%.

We also benchmark the current solution adopted in Vale to the proposed approaches in 12 real instances, eight from

LargePort and four from ComplexPort. Results show that GP+GRH provides competitive solutions for both ports compared to the company's algorithm, with an average throughput of 87.1% against 86.3%, respectively. Moreover, the computational time of the priority rules is, on average, four times shorter. This practical aspect is relevant to the company due to the need for rapid responses to unexpected events. Detailed results are presented in Section C from Appendix.

7.3. Managing uncertainty

In practice, wagon unloading operations are subject to several disruptions and unexpected events. Thus, methods must be developed to minimise or dynamically accommodate deviations. As discussed in Section 2, the scheduling literature presents very distinct approaches to deal with unexpected disruptions. The experiments of this section aim at providing guidance on the performance of predictive-reactive strategies under different uncertainty levels. In the application tackled in this work, changes on the original plan incur additional railway maneuvers and overhead. Managers seek a good compromise between maximising throughput and avoiding deviations from the planned schedule. Thus, we also analyse both objectives. Seven strategies are tested in 24-hours simulations. We classify them in three approaches:

- **Follow the baseline schedule:** The original plan is maintained as much as possible. As in Jain and Foley (2016), we evaluate rigid (*Baseline*) and flexible schemes (*Baseline with flexibility*). The rigid strategy respects the original car dumper and sequence of each lot. Thus, delays in the earlier operations highly affect the subsequent ones. In case of adopting the *Baseline with flexibility*, one may change the assigned car dumpers and anticipate lots. Thus, when deciding the next operation, a strategy n -flexible seek lots at most n positions distant in the original schedule. We simulate $n = 1$ and 2.
- **Periodic re-scheduling:** The system periodically re-schedules the remaining lots, and the last schedule is fixed until the next re-scheduling. For generating new partial schedules, the algorithm described in Section 5.1 is applied. Three re-scheduling intervals are considered: 12 hours, 6 hours and 3 hours.
- **Use dispatching rules:** We apply the rules evolved with GP to select the next operation once machines are available. When prioritising operations, the rules take into account the original schedule to avoid deviations.

In all experiments, the baseline schedule is the best solution found by any of the proposed methods (MIP, CP or GRH). Each point in the charts represents the average result of 20 replications of each of the 120 instances. This number of replications is sufficient for a 0.05 significance level (guaranteeing an error of at most 0.5 on both metrics).

The charts of Figure 5 show results obtained with instances from ComplexPort, and six levels of uncertainty. When $cv = 0$ (processing times are deterministic), no strategy is necessary, and the throughput corresponds to the baseline. The dispatching rule used is DR_CP (c.f. Section 7.1). As expected, maintaining the baseline schedule in a rigid strategy produces the highest deterioration in the throughput but no deviations. At low uncertainty levels, it seems

that following the baseline with some flexibility or re-scheduling are both good approaches. As uncertainty increases, the performance of the dispatching rule tends to be more competitive. Overall, re-scheduling with high frequency is the best strategy to maximise the throughput. However, we observed that re-scheduling produces a high number of deviations. This result is consistent with the analysis of Sabuncuoglu and Bayız (2000) for flexible manufacturing systems. At high uncertainty levels, the use of DR_CP reduces the number of changes while providing the second-best result in throughput.

Figure 5: Simulation of wagons unloading with uncertain processing times in instances from ComplexPort

In the charts of Figure 6b, the output of instances from LargePort is presented. Two dispatching rules are considered, DR_LP1 and DR_LP2, both shown in Section 7.1. In general, the curves are similar to those from the previous experiments, and the overall conclusion is the same. In this case, the re-scheduling approach is even more effective than the others. Surprisingly, in medium-low uncertainty levels re-scheduling at every six hours produces better throughput than following the baseline with flexibility. We suspect that this is due to the several eligible routes of each lot. Even maintaining the original car dumpers and sequence for six hours, one can find alternative routes without overlap. This is not possible in ComplexPort as lots have a limited number of eligible routes there.

We also evaluate the effect of the trains' arrivals on the performance of the strategies. The frequency of train arrivals depends on u , which is an upper bound for utilisation of car dumpers. Instances with low values of u have fewer trains and lots. In Figure 7, we present results of three groups of instances, with low, medium and high machines utilisation (all from ComplexPort). In those simulation experiments, the mean machines utilisation is 41%, 49% and 59%, respectively for u equals to 0.6, 0.8 and 1.2. Observe that with a smaller number of trains (Figure 7a), the

Figure 6: Simulation of wagons unloading with uncertain processing times in instances from LargePort

difference in the performance of the strategies is not as clear, although re-scheduling at every 3 hours seems the best for maximising the throughput. As the number of trains' arrivals increases, the distinction in the output of the strategies also increases. In congested settings, the performance of the dispatching rule is similar to re-scheduling every three hours. These results suggest that managers should be aware of the system behaviour and adapt strategies accordingly.

8. Conclusions and future work

In this paper, we studied product reception in bulk ports. In such process, wagons must be unloaded to stockpiles in a complex operation that requires the synchronisation of the machines involved. Moreover, there is uncertainty in processing times, as unexpected events frequently occur. Our study uses real data from a leading mining company and randomly generated instances to assess the performance of several solution approaches. The problem is formalised as a variant of the Multimode Multiprocessor Task Scheduling.

First, we designed two models for the deterministic version of the problem, a MIP and a CP. GP is also employed on the design of priority rules, which are applied by a greedy-randomised procedure, GRH. In the randomly generated instances, the rules, the CP and the MIP provide an average throughput of 78.1%, 75.2% and 47.0%, respectively. The MIP cannot find any integer solution in the real scenarios. These instances are also challenging for the CP algorithm, which finds solutions for only 93 out of 240 instances. CP tends to find better schedules in instances with few train arrivals, and the rules perform better in the opposite case. In comparison to the current solution used by

Figure 7: Simulation of distinct machines utilisation and the throughput obtained with each strategy

the mining company, the priority rules find similar solutions using only a quarter of the computational time. The overall conclusion is that, in general, GP+GRH outperforms the other methods. Moreover, we highlight the ease of implementing the priority rules, which have better prospects of being wide-adopted in practice than more sophisticated approaches.

Second, we also use GP to evolve dispatching rules for the stochastic version of the problem. The rules were designed with two objectives: maximising the operation's throughput and minimising deviations from a baseline schedule. GP is effective in finding rules that produce fewer deviations from the baseline. Third, we use simulation to evaluate several strategies for managing uncertainty. Three approaches are considered: maintaining the baseline schedule (in rigid and flexible schemes), periodic re-scheduling and the dispatching rules. We concluded that frequent re-scheduling provides better throughput than the other strategies. However, as uncertainty increases, the rules generate competitive solutions. This effect is more prominent in settings with a high number of train arrivals. On the other hand, re-scheduling incurs several deviations, and the evolved rules present the best compromise between both objectives. Overall, we conclude that GP is an effective approach in both deterministic and stochastic cases: the automatically designed GRH heuristic outperforms the other methods; the designed rules present a competitive behaviour considering the throughput/deviations trade-off.

As GRH is a fast constructive algorithm, there is room for improving the solution quality by developing a local search. Future work should also be employed on other predictive-reactive strategies, such as the pairwise exchange heuristic proposed by Jain and Foley (2016). Moreover, delays in the expected train arrivals influence the performance of the schedule. One should incorporate this stochastic aspect into the problem. Finally, alternative models for counting the number of schedule deviations may be also be considered.

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A. Genetic Programming algorithm

The pseudo-code of the proposed GP is provided in Algorithm 2. The algorithm receives as input the training instance set I . The output is the best individual found a^* , from which the best dispatching rule r^* is obtained. In line 1, the initial population is created using the method Ramped Half-and-Half (Koza, 1994). In this method, trees are randomly created by combining two methods, "full" and "grow", with equal probability. In trees created by the "full" method, the path length from the root to every terminal is equal to a pre-specified maximum depth. The "grow" method instead generates trees with variable shapes and sizes. In lines 2 to 11, the algorithm performs the generational evolution: at each generation g , the population P_g is evaluated and updated. The fitness of each individual a is calculated by simulating the corresponding rule r on the training set (line 6). For each instance $i \in I$, the simulator returns the average throughput obtained (τ_{ai}). The fitness of a combines both metric and the tree size $|a|$ (line 8). As the weight of the penalty size depends on g , in line 9 the algorithm recalculates the fitness of the best individual found so far (a^*).

In line 11, the next generation's population is created from the current population P_g and the genetic operators. There are two breeding pipelines, crossover and mutation, and each one is applied according to a probability. The crossover pipeline selects two individuals as parents to produce two offspring. This operation selects a node at random in each tree and swaps the two sub-trees rooted by those nodes. Mutation replaces a sub-tree with a randomly generated one, generating a new individual. Both pipelines use tournament for parent selection, returning the best

Algorithm 2: Genetic Programming algorithm

Input: Training set I and solutions S

Result: Dispatching rule r^*

```
1 Initialise population  $P_g$ ;  
2 for  $g = 1$  to  $max\_g$  do  
3   foreach individual  $a \in P_g$  do  
4      $r \leftarrow decode\ a$ ;  
5     foreach instance  $i \in I$  do  
6        $\tau_{ai} \leftarrow simulate(r, i, S_i)$ ;  
7      $\tau_a = 1/|I| \cdot \sum_{i \in I} \{\tau_{ai}\}$ ;  
8      $fitness(a, g) = \tau_a + dev_a \cdot \delta + |a| \cdot g \cdot \rho$ ;  
9   Calculate fitness of  $a^*$  in  $g$ ;  
10   $a^* \leftarrow \arg \min_{a \in \{P_g \cup a^*\}} fitness(a, g)$ ;  
11   $P_{g+1} \leftarrow Crossover\ and\ mutation\ in\ P_g$ ;
```

of ts individuals selected at random (ts is said tournament size). The breeding process picks certain kinds of nodes with different probabilities. For example, one can state to pick non-terminals 90% of the time and terminals 10% of the time. The algorithm runs until it reaches a maximum number of generations max_g and returns the best individual found a^* .

B. Fictitious ports

Table 11 presents the characteristics of all instances based on fictitious ports. Three distinct settings are considered for training GP and six for the validation of the methods. For each combination of <#car dumpers - #stackers - #conveyors - #routes> and number of products, we generated 10 instances for training and 20 for validation. Stochastic instances also consider the cv parameter, which represents the coefficient of variation of processing times.

Table 11: Parameters of the randomly generated ports

	Training set	Validation set
<#car dumpers - #stackers - #conveyors - #routes>	<3 - 3 - 3 - 7>, <5 - 5 - 5 - 31>, <7 - 7 - 7 - 54>	<4 - 4 - 4 - 16>, <4 - 6 - 6 - 36>, <5 - 5 - 5 - 31>, <5 - 7 - 7 - 61>, <6 - 6 - 6 - 54>, <6 - 8 - 8 - 96>
Number of products	4, 16	2, 10, 20
Machines utilisation (u)	0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2	0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4
Instances per setting	10	20
# Deterministic instances	240	2160
Variation in processing times (cv)	0.4, 0.8	0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0
# Stochastic instances	480	10800

C. Real instances

Table 12 presents a performance comparison between the proposed approaches and the current solution adopted by Vale. The algorithm used by the company constructs an initial solution and improves it by using a large 3-opt neighbourhood search. We benchmark the methods using 12 real instances of two ports: LargePort and ComplexPort. Despite the limited number of instances, GP seems competitive to the current algorithm used in the company. The priority rules find similar solutions in a much shorter computational time.

Table 12: Performance comparison on the real instances

Port	Horizon (hz)	#Lots	#Wagons	Current solution		CP		GP + GCH	
				Throughput	Time (s)	Throughput	Time (s)	Throughput	Time (s)
LargePort	2382	83	7798	100.0%	198	-	-	100.0%	46
	1878	89	8446	90.4%	318	-	-	89.7%	67
	1691	85	8500	81.3%	320	-	-	88.8%	97
	1045	65	6046	64.8%	192	-	-	68.2%	24
	1045	57	5338	72.2%	139	-	-	68.0%	73
	542	35	2846	100.0%	94	-	-	100.0%	7
	1598	81	7910	79.8%	305	-	-	89.5%	39
	942	60	5492	64.5%	198	-	-	56.9%	22
Total/Average				81.6%	221	-	-	82.6%	47
ComplexPort	2734	35	2448	100.0%	17	96.6%	3646	100.0%	0
	2734	36	2468	100.0%	13	100.0%	2059	100.0%	1
	1294	32	2190	83.0%	16	84.8%	3625	84.2%	0
	885	28	1784	100.0%	10	100.0%	779	100.0%	1
	Total/Average				95.8%	14	95.4%	2527	96.1%